

SiEU Green
Sino-European innovative green
and smart cities

Sino-European Innovative Green and Smart Cities

Deliverable 6.3

Promotional material

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SiEUGreen

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research, and Innovation programme, under grant Agreement N 774233 and from the Chinese Ministry of Science and Technology.

Throughout SiEUGreen's implementation, EU and China will share technologies and experiences, thus contributing to the future developments of urban agriculture and urban resilience in both continents.

The project SiEUGreen aspires to enhance the EU-China cooperation in promoting urban agriculture for food security, resource efficiency and smart, resilient cities.

The project contributes to the preparation, deployment and evaluation of showcases in 5 selected European and Chinese urban and peri-urban areas: a previous hospital site in Norway, community gardens in Denmark, previously unused municipal areas with dense refugee population in Turkey, big urban community farms in Beijing and new green urban development in Changsha Central China.

A sustainable business model allowing SiEUGreen to live beyond the project period is planned by joining forces of private investors, governmental policy makers, communities of citizens, academia and technology providers.

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 facebook.com/SiEUGreen2020

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 linkedin.com/groups/8652505

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Technical References

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¹ **PU** = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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Introduction

Global urbanization has started to affect rural environments and as a result, agriculture has been reduced. A solution to this problem, has been advised to be, the development of urban agriculture techniques. Thus, the Sino-European Innovative Green and Smart Cities (SiEUGreen) project was created.

According to the project, urban farming will create many social and economic opportunities that will be beneficial to be investigated and analyzed. Due to that fact, a consortium of nineteen European and Chinese partners were brought together in order to decide on how the project will be put to practice. One of the main tasks is the efficient communication between the partners and the dissemination of the project by using different methods and tools.

This report was created as a part of the Work Package 6 – Communication and Dissemination, Deliverable 6.3: Promotional Material. For the purpose of promoting the project in the most efficient way, different methods were used and presented. All possible ways of successfully promoting the project can be considered, including some more traditional ones such as press releases, use of leaflets and posters, as well as some other, like YouTube videos. These methods, along with the tools that have been used are being analysed in the following chapters.

Deliverable 6.3 Promotional material

Motivational and training material

This deliverable includes all the required material for raising awareness on environmental challenges due to rural agriculture, food security and the opportunity that Urban Agriculture (UA) has to offer. In order to do so, the following tools were used, each one of them being analyzed in a following chapter:

- Short YouTube videos,
- Leaflets,
- Posters,
- Roll-up Banners &
- Press Release.

Short YouTube Videos

A YouTube Chanel was created under the name “SiEUGreen Horizon 2020” that can be found [here](#). Nine videos information on the SiEUGreen project and other urban agriculture techniques, were created and posted on the channel. All videos were posted on December 27th 2018 and English subtitles are available when the video is in a language different than English.

Video 1: Professor Petter D Jenssen from the NMBU analyses how Toilets can save lives

Figure 1: Professor Petter D. Jenssen explains how toilets can save lives

Professor Petter D Jenssen from the NMBU analyses how Toilets can save lives, because human waste spreads killer diseases and how flush toilets can drive to a zero waste, recycling model, for the creation of biogas and other by-products, e.g. fertilizer.

Video 2: Sanitation + Animation = Sanimation

Figure 2: Sanitation and Animation, a short video created by NMBU students

NMBU students create a very interesting animated video on an innovative approach on Sanitation worldwide and how water based centralised systems can be transformed into more hygienic and civilised ones.

Video 3: Sanyuan farm Beijing

Figure 3: The Sanyuan farm in Beijing

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Video clip of Sanyuan farm, in Beijing, showing part of the project's showcase there. Because during its filming it was wintertime in Beijing, there's not any vegetables in the urban mini-gardens.

Video 4: Transformation of Cicignon Park, Fredrikstad Norway

Figure 4: How the Cicignon Park will be developed

The video shows the Cicignon Park, in Fredrikstad Norway, after its giant green transformation will be completed. The maquette of the video has been prepared for the MIPIM Cannes conference 2018.

Video 5, Video 6 & Video 7: Aarhus Case Faellesgartneriet Drone Videos

Figure 5: Community garden in Aarhus as seen from a Drone

At this site over 100 people are farming. They come from all over Aarhus. One thing that they do have in common is the need of ground, space and facilities to grow. They also seek for the community which “Fællesgartneriet” provides.

Video 8: Show case in Changsha

Figure 6: The expected creation of the Changsha farm

The video for the show case in Changsha, by A-AQUA AS, depicts the transformation of the local project.

Video 9: Aquaponics, fish and plants in the same system

Figure 7: Aquaponics system in Landvik, Norway

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An aquaponics' construction consists of a plant unit and a fish unit in one system. The fish water runs into the plant unit, the fish is in the blue tanks and the water runs from there into the plants' section. Researcher Siv Lene Gangenes Skar in NIBIO explains how it works. The video is from NIBIO's research facility in Landvik, in Grimstad municipality, Norway.

Figure 8: SAMPAS presentation for the SIEUGreen Project

Figure 9: Mrs Athanasiou describes the activities of KIPOS3 Project

Figure 10: Mrs Gavriilidou explains the establishment of KIPOS3 Project

Leaflets

Leaflets were designed in order to promote the SiEUGreen project and its objectives. The design was sent to all partners to be printed and used in different occasions such as conferences, meetings etc., as each organization sees fit. Around 110 copies in total were distributed during two different occasions, 70 of them were used in the AgriResearch Conference in Brussels on May 2nd-3rd 2018. It was attended by approximately 500 people and its main theme was the advancement of urban agriculture in Europe and rural research and innovation techniques now and in the future.

The other 40 copies were distributed in the workshop organized in Thessaloniki on November 22nd 2018 with the title “Trends Scanning Workshop: An interactive workshop for the identification of trends and emerging business models of Urban Farming”. During the workshop, a discussion took place, regarding future trends that will affect societies and the development of urban agriculture.

The actual leaflets can be found in an Annex in the current document.

Figure 11: Photos from the Trends Scanning Workshop, held in Thessaloniki

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Poster

A poster was also designed and distributed to all partners for promoting the project. It can be used in activities like conferences, workshops and different events that include a presentation or a promotion of any kind. Each one of the partner can print the poster in their own convenience and use it for their own purposes.

Figure 12: The poster for the SiEUGreen project

Roll-up Banners

Two roll-up banners were created for the purpose of promoting the SiEUGreen project. They were and will be used in various activities such as conferences, workshops, etc. They were present in the 2nd Executive Board Meeting that was held in Thessaloniki as well as in the Workshop that followed, titled “Trends Scanning Workshop: An interactive workshop for the identification of trends and emerging business models of Urban Farming”, as seen in the pictures.

Figure 13: Roll-up banners in the Executive Board Meeting and the Workshop that followed

Press Release

A press statement was released in the Greek media (in the website <http://greenagenda.gr/>), in order to promote the SiEUGreen project and its result during the first year of its implementation. More specifically, the statement presented some generic information about the project and focused more on the activities that were accomplished during the period January 1st 2018 – January 1st 2019. The press release, in Greek, can be found in the following [link](#).

The text of the released statement can be found in Annex I, translated in English.

The translated text was sent to every member of the consortium, leaving the last paragraph free for every partner to complete its role in the project and then to be distributed to the media of each one country.

Accessories

Accessories which have the SiEUGreen's logo were designed, for the better and more efficient dissemination of the Project. Particularly, were designed:

- Notebook
- Pencil
- Usb stick
- Bags
- Budes
- T-shirt
- Caps

The promotional accessories are a strategic tool for the communication and dissemination of a Project, as they contribute in the introduction and raising of awareness for the Project, the instant recognition, the greater exposure in a larger audience and in general they drive citizens' interest in the desirable direction, which is the purposes of the Project and urban agriculture. The accessories which do not have the EU and Chinese Ministry sign will be reformed, by adding these signs or make any relevant changes, when they will be actually produced.

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Caps

T-Shirt

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Annex I - Actual Press Release in English

Thessaloniki, December 2018: One year will be marked on January 1st 2019 that the Sino-European Innovative Green and Smart Cities project (SiEUGreen) is in progress. Funded by the European Commission and the Chinese Ministry of Science and Technology, SiEUGreen is a project that aims in the research and development of urban agriculture techniques by building on the model of zero waste and circular economy and its total cost amounts to 7.7 million euros. The SiEUGreen project is a part of the larger Horizon2020 project, it is coordinated by the Norwegian University of Life Sciences and will run until December 31st 2021.

For the past year the EU and China have been exchanging methods and technologies contributing in the advancement of urban agriculture and urban resilience in both continents, and will continue to do so until the end of the project. However, the SiEUGreen project has been planned in such a way that even after 2021, people and communities will be able to continue engaging in the same activities since the infrastructure will continue to exist. In total, nineteen beneficiaries from Europe and China, including researchers, technology providers, local authorities and citizen communities, collaborate and overlook the execution of the project which is divided in many parts.

Cases that show how the different methods are to be implemented are already established in both Europe and China: in Denmark, Norway and Turkey, on one side, and in Beijing and Changsha on the other. Some of the places that are being used are an old hospital, unused buildings, municipal areas and community farms, and the practiced techniques include fertilizers produced from food waste, aquaponic and hydroponic cultures, paper-based plantations, greenhouses and many more.

The SiEUGreen project is based on the idea that the availability of rural areas is declining and that every city's surface can potentially be used. To that end, urban agriculture is considered to be one of the solutions that actually has an impact on societies and their members. Also, it is environmentally friendly since the circular economy plan leaves nothing to go to waste. So far, the majority of the work has been invested into preparing the implementation of the project, both as a whole and the individual parts of it, and the installment of the showcases where the selected methods are being put to use. After one year of practice, the first results are being gathered and are ready for analysis and evaluation. The results of the evaluation might affect the decision-making for a potential adjustment of the project's execution plan,

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since the different parts of the SiEUGreen project are expected to be completed in different time points.

One of the most important concepts, and the core idea of the SiEUGreen project, is the evolution of urban agriculture once the project is over. The advancement of the familiar techniques, as well as the creation of new ones, are the reason why this project started. Over the implementation period until the December of 2021, the foundations will be placed and after the project ends urban farming can expand in such a manner that it can become the main solution to people's need for food and at the same time clean the cities from their organic waste.

The dissemination and the communication of the project, both between the partners and between the partners and the public, has been trusted to Emetris SA, which is one of the nineteen beneficiaries of the project, located in Thessaloniki, Greece. Emetris SA also overlooks the task of analyzing, scanning and building scenarios for the future state of the urban agriculture landscape, by combining knowledge of the ecosystems, together with the technologies that are being developed and social and economic trends that affect them.

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Annex II - Actual Leaflet of the Project

SiEUGreen

Sino-European innovative green and smart cities

A NEW VISION

SiEUGreen in a nutshell - A new Vision

Taking into consideration challenges and opportunities presented by global urbanization, the SiEUGreen project brings together a multi-disciplinary Consortium of European and Chinese researchers, technology providers, SMEs, financiers, local and regional authorities and resident communities, in order to apply novel urban agricultural technological techniques new approaches for social engagement and investigate the economic, environmental and social benefits of urban agriculture (UA).

The project aspires to enhance the EU-China cooperation in promoting urban agriculture for food security, resource efficiency and smart, resilient cities. Throughout SiEUGreen's implementation, EU and China will share technologies and experiences, thus contributing to the future developments of urban agriculture and urban resilience in both continents. The project contributes to the preparation, deployment and evaluation of showcases in 5 selected European and Chinese urban and peri-urban areas.

- A previous hospital site in Norway.
- Community gardens in Denmark.
- Previously unused municipal areas with dense refugee population in Turkey.
- Big urban community farms in Beijing, China and
- A new green urban development in Changsha Central China.

SiEUGreen

Project at a glance

Acronym:

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EU contribution: 6,999,999, 38€
Call Identifier: SFS-48-2017

Topic:
Resource-efficient urban agriculture for multiple benefits – contribution to the EU-China Urbanisation Partnership

The SiEUGreen Innovation Principles

Building on the model of zero-waste and circular economy, SiEUGreen will combine technological and societal innovation, by providing innovative technological tools, novel methodologies for cultural and behavioral analysis and impact assessment tools. A sustainable business model allows the project to live beyond the project period is planned by joining force of private investors (owners of the properties and land), governmental policy makers, civil residents and academia as technology supporters.

Main Objectives

The SiEUGreen project will incorporate elements of digital Social Innovation, by enhancing resident participation and awareness raising through a gamification app and an interactive platform. This will facilitate the collection of important human data linked to the social and cultural changes expected to be generated at each of the local communities and at an international level by the implementation of the SiEUGreen showcases.

In the SiEUGreen project there is close interaction with the community therefore the ethical aspects are particularly important. The SiEUGreen consortium has analyzed the potential ethical considerations to be taken into account:

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- 01** Improve resilience of urban centers in Europe and China and increase food security
- 02** Develop and showcase novel resource efficient systems for horticultural production in urban and peri-urban environments in China and Europe.
- 03** Create a "bridge" of shared knowledge and best practices between Europe and China, through the collaboration of scientists, communities and policy-makers at both continents.
- 04** Create an active trans-disciplinary community of multiple actors: researchers/technology providers, public authorities, private actors, residents, local communities, SMEs.
- 05** Create new value chains and develop sustainable business models that can be replicable across regions and countries.
- 06** Develop evaluation methods to measure the economic, environmental and social impacts of urban farming and its value chains on the urban communities.
- 07** Raise awareness, communicate the results and promote the adoption of the "green - smart - inclusive city" model

Partners of the project

- 01** Norwegian University of Life Sciences Norway
- 02** Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research - NIBIO Norway
- 03** Institute of Vegetables and Flowers, Chinese Academy of Agricultural Sciences China (People's Republic of)
- 04** CREVIS SPRL Belgium
- 05** NORDREGIO Sweden
- 06** EMETRIS SYMVOULOI ANAPTYXIS ORGNOSIS KAI PLIOFORIKIS AE Greece
- 07** ARHUS KOMMUNE Denmark
- 08** VILABS (CY) LTD Cyprus
- 09** OKYS LTD Bulgaria

- 10** Beijing Agricultural Ecological Ideas Services Union China (People's Republic of)
- 11** Beijing Green Valley Sprout CO., LTD China (People's Republic of)
- 12** A-Aqua AS Norway
- 13** Hatay Metropolitan Municipality Turkey
- 14** Rural Development Institute, Chinese Academy of Social Sciences China (People's Republic of)
- 15** Sampas Bilisim Ve Iletisim Sistemleri Sanayi Ve Ticaret A.S. Turkey
- 16** Hunan Hengkai Environmental Protection Science & Technology Investment Co.Ltd China (People's Republic of)
- 17** SEECON INTERNATIONAL GMBH Switzerland
- 18** LEIBNIZ-INSTITUT FÜR GEMÜSE- UND ZIERPFLANZENBAU GROSSBEEREN/ERFURT EV Germany
- 19** Beijing Photon Science & Technology Co., Ltd. China (People's Republic of)

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